

A New Perspective on Geometric Series for Computing Applications

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Abstract: In today's world, the growing complexity of mathematical modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical equations for solving the most complex real-life problems. In this article, a new kind of geometric series is formulated for computing applications.

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1. Introduction

Geometric series played a vital role in differential and integral calculus at the earlier stage of development and still continues as an important part of the study in science, engineering, management and its applications. In this article, a new geometric series [1-6] is constructed for application [7] of computational science and engineering.

2. Novel Geometric Series

Theorem 2.1: Let R be a set of real numbers & $p \in R$. $\sum_{i=0}^n x^{pi} = \frac{x^{p(n+1)} - 1}{x^p - 1}, p \neq 0$.

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using a general term.

$$i. e., \quad x^{pn} = \frac{x^{p(n+1)} - x^{pn}}{x^p - 1} = \frac{x^{pn}(x^p - 1)}{x^p - 1}, p \neq 0. \quad (1)$$

By summing both sides of (1) with the limits from 0 to n , we express the same as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n x^{pi} = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{x^{p(i+1)} - x^{in}}{x^p - 1}, p \neq 0. \quad (2)$$

From the series (2), we conclude that $\sum_{i=0}^n x^{pi} = \frac{x^{p(n+1)} - 1}{x^p - 1}, p \neq 0$. (3)

Hence, theorem is proved.

If p is a non-negative integer in the series (3), the following lemma can be constituted for the application of computational science.

Lemma 2.1: $\sum_{i=0}^{p-1} x^i * \sum_{i=0}^n x^{pi} = \frac{x^{p(n+1)} - 1}{x - 1}$ ($x \neq 1$), where $*$ denotes multiplication.

Proof.

$$\sum_{i=0}^{p-1} x^i * \sum_{i=0}^n x^{pi} = \left(\frac{x^p - 1}{x - 1}\right) * \left(\frac{x^{p(n+1)} - 1}{x^p - 1}\right) = \frac{x^{p(n+1)} - 1}{x - 1}, x \neq 1. \quad (4)$$

Hence, the lemma is proved.

$$\text{Note that } \sum_{i=0}^{np} x^i = \frac{x^{pn+1} - 1}{x - 1}, x \neq 1. \quad (5)$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, a new kind of geometric series has been introduced for the application of computing science. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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